

The assigned structures II and III were confirmed from the elemental analyses, IR and PMR spectral data.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The PMR spectra were recorded in Perkin Elmer R12B spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard and CCl₄ as solvent.

4-Picolyll magnesium iodide (I)

Ethyl magnesium iodide (ethyl iodide, 0.05M; magnesium, 0.05M and diethyl ether, 100 ml) was added dropwise within 15 min to a solution of 4-picoline (0.05M in 100 ml dry di-n-butyl ether)^{1,2}. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously at the elevated temperature 120-30° for 4 hr when a heterogeneous red brown oil (I) was obtained.

1-(Pyridyl-4)-2-phenyl ethanol-2-(II) and 1-(Pyridyl-4)-2-methyl-propanol-2 (III)

Benzaldehyde and acetone were added to 4-picolyll-magnesium iodide separately at 0-5° with continuous stirring for 5 hr. The reaction mixtures were left over night and then again stirred for 1 hr at 50-60°. The crude products obtained after the usual treatment were separately distilled at 0.5 mm pressure and were identified as II (20% yield, b.p. 150°/0.5 mm, HCl salt-m.p. 210-12°)³ and III (15% yield, b.p. 135°/0.5 mm, HCl salt-m.p. 195°, picrate-m.p. 208°). The purity of these compounds were ascertained through TLC using EtOH : EtOAc : HCOOH (6 : 2 : 2) as mobile phase (Rf's : II, 0.75 ; III, 0.70).

IR spectra : II and III, 3400 cm⁻¹

PMR spectra : II- δ 7.1-7.6, 9H ; δ 3.9-4.4, 3H ; δ 5.85 (broad), 1H

III- δ 7.1-7.6, 4H ; δ 4.05, 2H ; δ 0.95, 6H ; δ 5.90, 1H

Elemental Analyses: Found : C, 66.36 ; H, 5.68 ; N, 5.86%. Calcd for C₁₃H₁₄ONCl (II.HCl) : C, 66.24 ; H, 5.94 ; N, 5.94%

Found : C, 57.56 ; H, 7.24 ; N, 7.32%. Calcd for C₉H₁₄ONCl (III.HCl) : C, 57.60 ; H, 7.46 ; N, 7.46%

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. D. KISHORE, P. K. KHANDELWAL and B. C. JOSHI, *Archiv. Des. Sci.*, 1974, 27, 39-41.
2. VON E. PROFFI and F. SCHNEIDER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1955, 2, 316-22.
3. A. N. KOST, A. K. SHEINKMAN and A. N. ROZENBERG, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1964, 34, 4046-54.

Synergic Extraction of Titanium(IV) in the Presence of Morin and Aniline**

K. SOBHANA and C. P. SAVARIAR*

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala 673635, India.

Manuscript received 6 April 1976, revised 23 August 1976, accepted 30 December 1976

MANY methods have been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of titanium¹⁻⁴. However, only few papers have been published on the synergic extraction of the ternary complex of titanium⁵⁻⁷. No work appears to be recorded on the extraction of Ti(IV)-morin chelate in the presence of aniline as synergist. It is observed in the present work that the addition of aniline to the extractant caused a considerable enhancement of the distribution ratio of titanium. Based on this, an accurate and simple extractive-spectrophotometric method is suggested for the determination of titanium(IV).

Experimental

A Bausch & Lomb Spec'ronic 20, with matched test tubes, was used for absorbance measurements. Toshniwal (India) pH meter was used for measurement of pH.

Titanium solution (1 mg Ti ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of AnalaR potassium titanyl oxalate in double distilled water containing 100 ml of 5N H₂SO₄ and making upto one litre. The metal content per ml was estimated gravimetrically by cupferron⁸.

A 0.05M solution of morin was prepared in 50% alcohol. Further dilutions were made as and when necessary.

All solvents including aniline were purified by distillation.

Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer was used.

*Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Roorkee 1975.

Ammonium Chloride (4M) was prepared in double distilled water. Solutions of divers ions were prepared from AnalaR chemicals.

Procedure: Place an aliquot of titanium(IV) solution containing about 10 μg of the metal in a separating funnel and add 2 ml of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer followed by 1-2 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the reagent. Then add 2-4 ml of 4M ammonium chloride. Shake the mixture gently for about 30 sec with 5 ml of a solution of 0.02M aniline in a 3 : 1 mixture of benzyl alcohol and butyl alcohol. Transfer the organic layer to a small beaker containing anhydrous sodium sulphate. Extract the aqueous layer again and collect in the same beaker. Transfer the combined extract to a 10-ml volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with the solvent. Measure the absorbance at 420 nm against the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Titanium-morin complex is extracted from sodium acetate acetic acid buffer in the pH range 3.2-4.1 with a mixture of benzyl alcohol and butyl alcohol in the ratio 3 : 1. The extracted species has an absorbance maximum at 420 nm. Addition of aniline to the solvent introduces a synergistic effect to the extraction system, though the absorbance maximum remains unchanged. Solvent, like chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene and xylene are unsuitable for extraction; but butyl alcohol, cyclohexanone and cyclohexanol can extract the complex. However, maximum extraction occurs when a mixture of benzyl alcohol and butyl alcohol in the ratio 3 : 1 is used.

Effect of reagent concentration: To obtain maximum colour intensity for the complex containing 9.6 μg of titanium, 1-1.5 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ morin solution is required which is about 20-30 times greater than the metal ion concentration.

Effect of electrolyte: Use of an electrolyte increased the efficiency of the extraction. Electrolytes like ammonium chloride, sodium chloride, aluminium sulphate, aluminium nitrate, sodium acetate, lithium chloride, ammonium sulphate are tried for their effect on the extraction. Ammonium chloride is found to be the most effective salting out agent and a 4M solution of it is used for subsequent work.

Effect of pH: Effect of pH on the extraction is studied over a wide range and it is observed that for the Ti-morin chelate the optimum pH is from 3.2-4.1 and for Ti-morin-aniline adduct the pH is from 3.9-4.6. A sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution is used for maintaining the pH.

Period of equilibration and stability of the complex: Extraction is quantitative after 30 sec of equilibration. Complex, extracted under optimum condition, is stable for about 20 hr and decomposes very slowly afterwards.

Sensitivity and molar absorptivity: The photometric sensitivity¹ of the method is 0.0012 $\mu\text{g Ti cm}^{-2}$ at 420 nm and the molar absorptivity of the complex is $3.8 \times 10^4 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$.

Composition of the complex: The composition of the Ti(IV)-morin-aniline complex is studied by different methods. In one case at different pH values, the log of the distribution ratio, E, of the metal ion against log [morin] is plotted at fixed concentration of aniline. The resulting straight lines gave slopes ranging from 2.5-3 indicating that three morin molecules participate in the complex formation (molar ratio Ti : morin = 1 : 3). Similarly the effects of variation of aniline concentration are studied at constant morin concentration. The slopes obtained from the plots of log E against log [aniline] show that only one molecule of aniline is added to the complex. Similarly the slopes obtained from the plots of log E against pH indicate that three protons are liberated in the complex formation. This again confirms that in the complex titanium to morin ratio is 1 : 3. So the sole extractable species under the experimental condition is Ti (morin)₃ aniline.

The composition of the complex is also established by the Job's method of continuous variation⁸ and mole ratio method¹⁰. Both the methods confirm the ratio of the extractable species as Ti : morin : aniline = 1 : 3 : 1.

Interference of various ions: No interference is found with Ce^{4+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , and Cr^{3+} in 500-fold excess. Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Zr^{4+} and Mn^{2+} are tolerated upto 500 times in presence of slight amount of borate. Be^{2+} and Mo^{6+} are tolerated in 100-fold excess, and U^{6+} , V^{5+} , Th^{4+} and W^{6+} in 15-fold amounts. Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} can be masked in 100-fold amounts with trace amount of ascorbic acid. Cu^{2+} and Nb^{5+} interfere seriously.

Determination of titanium in ilmenite; About 1 g of finely powdered ilmenite is accurately weighed and fused with 10 g of sodium bisulphate in a silica crucible. The cold cake is extracted with 500 ml of a saturated solution of ammonium acetate. This solution is diluted twenty times with water. Aliquots of the diluted solution is used for spectrophotometric determinations. Iron present is masked by adding trace quantities of ascorbic acid. Results are compared with hydrogen peroxide method¹¹ and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TITANIUM IN ILMENITE

Method	% TiO ₂ found		Mean
	(1)	(2)	
Synergistic	57.10	59.00	58.05
Hydrogen peroxide	58.80	58.10	58.45

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K. S.) is grateful to the University of Calicut for the award of U.G.C. Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1965.
2. J. E. SCHWARZBERG and R. W. MOSHIER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, 34, 525.
3. N. N. GHOSH and A. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 972.
4. C. P. SAVARIAR and JOY JOSEPH, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1969, 47, 347.
5. A. I. BUSEV, T. D. ALIZADE and N. G. SOLOVE'VA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1972, 27, 692.
6. A. I. BUSEV and N. G. SOLOVE'VA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1962, 27, 1100.
7. A. K. BABKO, *Talanta.*, 1968, 15, 721.
8. L. ERDEY, "Gravimetric Analysis", Pergamon Press, New York, 1965, Part II, p. 464.
9. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, 9, 113.
10. Y. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
11. W. R. SCHOELLER and A. R. POWELL, "Analysis of Minerals and Ores of the Rare Elements", Charles Griffin and Co., London, 1955, p. 124.

Effect of Temperature on the Rate of Coagulation of Ferric Tellurate, Chromium Tellurate and Vanadium Pentaoxide Hydrosols by Viscometric Technique

MUKHTAR SINGH & O. P. BANSAL

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra.

Manuscript received 6 January 1976, revised 21 July 1976,
accepted 30 December 1976

RECENTLY, Ghosh and coworkers have studied the effect of temperature on the coagulation of thorium oxide and ceric oxide hydrosols and have interpreted their results with the help of an equation, relating time of slow coagulation (t_s) and temperature, based on the theory of stability of colloids developed by Fuchs², Derjaguin³ and Overbeek⁴.

The equation derived is

$$\log t_s = \frac{N(E + V_{max})}{2.303 RT} + B \quad (1)$$

From equation (1) it is clear that a plot $\log t_s$ against $1/T$ should give a straight line.

In this communication an attempt has been made to verify this equation and thereby obtain the maximum value of the potential energy barrier, V_{max} , for the coagulation of ferric tellurate, chromium tellurate and vanadium pentaoxide hydrosols.

Experimental

(a) Preparation of sols :

Positively charged hydrosols of ferric tellurate and chromium tellurate were prepared, according to the method reported in our earlier publication⁵, and were subsequently dialysed.

Negatively charged vanadium pentaoxide hydrosol was prepared by treating about 15 g. ammonium vanadate with 15 ml Conc. HNO_3 in a porcelain basin with constant stirring. The precipitate so formed was then filtered off and well washed with water till the dark red sludge began to give red colour in the filtrate. The precipitate was then transferred to a conical flask and was shaken in a litre of water to convert it into a dark red coloured sol, which was subjected to dialysis.

(b) Determination of rate of coagulation :

The rate of coagulation of the sols was determined viscometrically. Viscosity measurements were made by Scarpa's method⁶ modified by Farrow⁷ and improved by Prasad and coworkers⁸. The temperature was controlled using a Gallenkamp thermostat. The progress of coagulation was detected by recording changes in viscosity. The sol and the electrolyte were taken in a number of viscometers placed simultaneously in the thermostated bath. After a desired interval of time the viscosity of the coagulating system was found out in one viscometer and at the subsequent interval in the other viscometer and so on. This was done only to avoid the disturbances in the system during the process of coagulation. However, the uncertainties involved in viscosity measurement cannot be ruled out. For each set of observations 5 ml of a mixture of water and electrolyte of known concentration was added to 5 ml of the sol (total volume being 10 ml in each case) and the viscosity was determined at different intervals. Several sets of observations were taken with different concentrations of coagulating electrolyte, but the concentrations of the electrolyte were so adjusted that the time of coagulation was of the order of 5 to 80 minutes. This was considered as the time of slow coagulation. The whole process was repeated at different temperatures. The relative change of viscosity was determined by the ratio $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$ where η_0 is the initial viscosity and η is the viscosity at the end of the interval time t' . This ratio was taken according to Freundlich⁹ and Gann¹⁰ as a measure of relative increase in coagulation.

The points of inflexion in the curves obtained by plotting $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$ (i.e., degree of coagulation, x) against time were

taken to denote same stage of coagulation ($\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = 0$)

brought about by adding different concentrations of the electrolyte. The times corresponding to points of inflexion were taken as the times¹¹ of slow coagulation corresponding to a definite stage of coagulation.